

THE ROLE OF ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERSHIP IN JOB SATISFACTION AT THE WORKPLACE

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Abstract

Objective: The study aimed to identify the impact and role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction for employees in the Saudi Telecom Company. **Method:** The descriptive analytical approach was used, where data and information were collected. The questionnaire was used as a tool for collecting data. A simple random sample was taken from the research community, who are employees of the Saudi Telecom Company, a selection of (92) employees. **Result:** The study's results showed that administrative leadership's role in achieving job satisfaction was high. The study also showed a strong connection between the dimensions of managerial leadership and achieving job satisfaction. **Conclusion:** Adopting modern management methods and concepts that enable companies to keep pace with technological developments and help them achieve job satisfaction and thus achieve excellence and performance.

Keywords: Administrative Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Workplace, Saudi Telecom.

INTRODUCTION

The history of leadership is as old as history, yet the study of management did not start until the latter few decades of the 1800s. On the other hand, management science, of which leadership is a subfield, is concerned with four primary processes: organizing, leading and supervising, controlling, and planning.

The capacity to motivate a group of people, organize their activities, and guide them toward objectives is known as leadership (Amanchukwu et al., 2015). The history of humanity predates the leadership process, which has existed since the earliest social interactions. That is impossible to overstate the significance of management and administrative leadership in any endeavour requiring a large workforce (Perry & Christensen, 2015). When leaders are present, there is both psychological support and task support. Psychological support is the first aid in problem-solving and confidence building, and task support is provided by resource organization and assistance in completing tasks in accordance with the required criteria (Liao & Chuang, 2007).

Fostering cooperation and inspiring teamwork and non-individual work by providing each member with a fair and structured leadership environment (Rajanayakam, 2010). The presence of leaders fosters self-assurance, desire, and excitement in both individuals and groups, supporting their growth and contentment in their jobs (Connelly et al., 2013). A leader's presence also boosts learning and experience chances and provides the person hope to take on a new role in their career (Hanshaw & Hanson, 2018). One of the most crucial functions and justifications for a leader's existence is discipline.

Input on the steps people have taken to encourage the right things and offer guidance and adjustment for the incorrect things. The involvement of leaders facilitates the addition of new laws and other organizational changes and the development of a sensible and moral role model (Day et al., 2008). Thus, it leads to job satisfaction among employees in the workplace.

Interest in the topic of job satisfaction and how it affects people's behaviour dates back to Frederick M. Taylor's efforts to improve organizational efficiency (Bauman & Skitka, 2012). In order to accomplish this, he advocated for collaboration and responsibility sharing between management and employees. Taylor's theories, which ended with the prospect of raising production, had an impact on the relationship (Elsheikh et al., 2014). By enhancing their performance at work, the employees, and subsequently the earnings of people who are accountable for them, according to Taylor, worker satisfaction would rise and be attained whenever the level of fatigue subsided or the wage was raised (Croucher et al., 2013).

Many definitions exist for the term "job satisfaction." It is the collection of favourable emotional sentiments that a person has toward his or her work or profession and conveys the level of personal fulfilment that employment brings (Matthews et al., 2018). In order to increase senior management's views toward fostering a sense of greater loyalty and belonging inside the company, job satisfaction is crucial in providing concepts, ideas, and opinions related to employee satisfaction levels (Vlachos et al., 2013). Additionally, working to raise training requirements enhances pay, salaries, and supervision in order to enhance and develop workers' individual and collective skill sets (Dobre, 2013).

This study was carried out because the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia had to deal with a number of economic developments and challenges, which prompted the creation of numerous agencies and businesses to boost the country's economy and attract more inhabitants and tourists. Consequently, this study's significance arises from the fact that it is one of the cutting-edge and contemporary issues affecting the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's businesses and economy. It also serves as a contribution to the scientific research endeavour in this crucial area, which still requires further study and analysis. The study's significance stems from the fact that administrative leadership is crucial, and its volume rises when it is connected to job satisfaction. The importance of the study is further increased by the different departments' goals of achieving good management and high levels of job satisfaction.

On the other hand, the problem of the study is to investigate the role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction in the workplace. As for the originality of this study, one of the most difficult and complex matters is human relations, as it is necessary to deal with different ages, cultures, and ideas and impose laws on them, build barriers, make things more integrated and easy, or organize them to accomplish and achieve a goal, and that is when the goal is to achieve something by having There is a need for several people. Here lies the problem and the utmost requirement for administrative leadership. Employee satisfaction in the workplace must be ensured.

Objectives of the study: This study aimed to know the level of administrative development of leaders in achieving job satisfaction and the role and relationship of good administrative leadership to job satisfaction.

Theoretical framework

Leadership is the art of influence. It is the social influence relationship between two or more individuals who are bound together by a particular group and who depend on one another to accomplish shared objectives (Haslam et al., 2020). However, how can leaders effectively influence others? The ability of an individual to affect others' motivations, opinions, and behaviours is known as social influence or interaction. When one asks, "How do leaders affect their followers?" this is the response. What gives a leader his authority and power is the social influence that he or she possesses.

Also, the leader's sphere of influence differs from the sum of the forces at his disposal. Different types of power produce different forms of compliance (Cartwright, 2013). For example, leaders who rely on coercive power cause followers to reject them or resist attempts to influence them. In contrast, leaders who rely on reward power produce followers who carefully consider their responses in order to obtain. The leader is satisfied and thus receives rewards.

There is a correlation between prevalent leadership philosophies and overall job satisfaction, with democratic leadership accounting for 37.5% of the variance, procedural leadership explaining 30% of the variance, transformational leadership accounting for 25.6% of the variance, and laissez-faire leadership accounting for 19.4% of the variance. Job satisfaction varies (Njoroge, 2015). That is a strong relationship between motivational communication, individual recognition, encouraging leadership, vision, and job happiness. However, intellectual stimulation has no beneficial effect on work satisfaction. The relationship between employee motivation and job satisfaction is also important. This study also demonstrates that only encouraging leadership boosts staff motivation. Managers of tourism businesses can use the findings as a guide to develop their knowledge, skills, and leadership abilities (Vinh et al., 2023).

The monitoring of both poor and positive practices in the area of communication between the leader and the work team was highlighted by Mirdad's (2018) research. The researcher noted employee responses in unfavourable and positive situations, whether these reactions increased employee job satisfaction, which increased loyalty and belonging, or decreased employee productivity. This study also made clear the extent to which a leader's capacity for effective team communication impacts job satisfaction. The study's conclusions included the need for developing professional programs to train leaders and emphasizing the use of leadership communication skills.

Al-Enezi et al.'s (2018) study also uncovered a link between leadership and job satisfaction, showing that effective leadership boosts the degree of job satisfaction at work and enhances it. However, Abdel Kamel et al. (2020) found patterns of administrative leadership in their investigation. It also demonstrated the idea of job satisfaction and the key federal leadership elements that influence job satisfaction at work, including seniority-based hiring standards and

controls, fostering an environment conducive to open communication and teamwork, and promoting employee disclosure. On the basis of a sense of fulfilment and loyalty, their ideas include establishing job criteria and paying attention to employees' physical and psychological needs.

A recommended scenario to fulfil this position was presented in Al-Sahli's study from 2021, which also demonstrated the importance of leadership in obtaining job happiness. This study clarified the value of leadership and how it contributes to workplace job happiness. Additionally, Saliha et al.'s study (2021) showed that socialist leadership affects job satisfaction. This effect is evident in creating an environment where understanding and interdependence between managers and staff are the norm, ensuring that the institution can treat both female and male employees fairly and paying attention to the human relations sector.

After reviewing several studies, it is evident that one of the most significant factors influencing the process of accomplishing goals that call for teamwork among many people is management. Without high levels of job satisfaction, cooperative work involving many people is not accomplished well in terms of quality, returns, and productivity. The most effective techniques for gauging satisfaction in any facility or organization are regular inquiries and surveys. Training, lectures, seminars, and publications that prepare people for collaborative work and provide management with the knowledge they need to grow and attain job satisfaction are all necessary to promote that fulfilment.

METHODOLOGY

This part contains the research methodology and procedures, clarification of the study population and its characteristics, definition of the study population and sample, how to build the study tool to collect the information necessary for the study, the scientific procedures used, the validity and reliability of the study tool, as well as the statistical methods that will be used in analyzing the data that will be obtained from the sample members. The study relied on the descriptive analytical method as it is the closest and most appropriate to the application of this research, which is concerned with studying problems related to the human and social fields. The researcher collected accurate information about a specific phenomenon that is the subject of the study, described that phenomenon and interpreted it accurately in terms of the available facts, as the researcher collected data about the role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction in the Saudi Telecom Company. Specific questions were developed and formulated in the form of a questionnaire, which will be distributed to the sample members, and then this data will be described and analyzed.

On the other hand, defining the research population the study targets is the first stage in every research project; the population represents the study's target elements in society, which is the researcher's chosen subset. All Saudi Telecom Company personnel make up the research population. The sample consists of subsets of society chosen in accordance with particular statistical guidelines and precepts. A basic random sample was drawn among the research population: Saudi Telecom Company employees. The questionnaire was disseminated electronically to the company's employees, and the number of those who answered the

questionnaire was a sample of (92) male and female employees. That Is done through an electronic form via the Google Drive website, then sending the electronic link to the intended sample via mobile phone applications, email, and social networking sites.

Regarding data collection techniques, main and secondary data are the two categories of data that the research uses to get the required data. Primary data: By creating an opinion survey to find out what the Saudi Telecom Company's employees think about the contribution of administrative leadership to job satisfaction, a sample of these employees was asked to complete the questionnaire. Secondary data: Using published books, journals, and letters, one can review prior research and ascertain the theoretical underpinnings of the current study.

A questionnaire is the instrument used to collect all data. As one of the most significant and widely used instruments for scientific research across many scientific domains, the questionnaire was the primary means of gathering study data from the sample participants. In addition to being more efficient than other approaches in terms of time savings, cost savings, and the ability to gather data on the greatest number of people, it also makes it easier for respondents to respond to some questions that take some time to complete. A list of questions was created for this study after the researcher studied prior research and theoretical literature pertaining to the study's topic. The questionnaire is split into two primary sections, with the aim of achieving the research objectives. Was chosen by the investigator to be used as a study tool which measures Explaining the role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction in the Saudi Telecom Company. Following that, the statements' responses were graded: A five-point Likert scale was used to grade the responses, with the following categories receiving scores: strongly disagree, agree, disagree, neutral, and highly agree (5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1), respectively.

Based on the total sample size of (92) people, the researcher computed the internal consistency of the questionnaire by reading the honesty test results (Pearson correlation coefficient) and calculating the correlation coefficients between each dimension item and the sub-dimensions overall score. At a significance level of 1%, the researcher determined that the probability value of the test for all the questionnaire items given to the sample participants was statistically significant. As the probability value for each dimension is less than 1%, all of the questionnaire's items are considered true for what it was intended to measure. The correlation coefficient values in all of the questionnaire's items and the overall average of its items are statistically significant at a significant level ≤ 0.01 α between the score of each item and the total score of the axis, according to the test set for that.

The researcher utilized Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to assess the degree of stability of the instrument in order to measure the reliability of the questionnaire or the extent to which the same results are produced, even if the study is repeated under comparable circumstances and with the same questionnaire. In order to guarantee the stability of the measures used, the results produced by the statistical package (SPSS) display the values of Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The scale is more stable when the values of this factor are closer to the right value; conversely, when the values are closer to zero, the scale is less stable. The findings demonstrated that the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for each variable (axes) was extremely high (88%),

indicating a high degree of reliability for the scale used as the study's instrument. That also suggests that the statements are objective and can accurately represent the variables they are measuring. Furthermore, it is obvious that the questionnaire needs to be used confidently; if the study is redone with the same sample, the same conclusions will be drawn.

In order to obtain frequencies, percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviations to answer the study hypotheses and describe the study sample, the questionnaires were coded and entered into the computer using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences program. That is because the software is best suited for analyzing the study data in a scientific manner that meets the study's objectives and tests its hypotheses.

The study analyzed the primary data for the research, described the research variables, and examined hypothesis testing using analytical descriptive statistics techniques. Arithmetic means, standard deviations, frequencies, percentages, and other statistical tests are computed. Figuring out the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to assess the questionnaire's dependability. Additionally, the degree of relationship between paragraphs can be assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient test. Regression analysis is used to calculate the correlation and effect between the variables under consideration. Next, the findings were retrieved using the computer and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS V. 23) program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The answer the study's main question, which states (What is the role of administrative leadership in job satisfaction in the Saudi Telecom Company?), the general average of the tool as a whole and its standard deviation were calculated. It was revealed through the degree of agreement for the tool, which was high, with an arithmetic mean of (3.7885) and a standard deviation. (0.7216), that shown in table (1).

Table 1: It shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the variables of the study tool

No.	Variables	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Administrative Leadership	3.93	0.88
2	Job Satisfaction	3.94	0.65
Total		3.78	0.72

That was found that the extent of administrative leadership in the Saudi Telecom Company in terms of extent was high, with an arithmetic mean (of 3.93) and a standard deviation (0.88). That is because the management keeps up with anything fresh. After all, they are eager to develop and improve. The goal of management is to inspire staff members and foster their creativity. The administration is in favour of fresh approaches to enhance output. The management offers training programmers for advancement and betterment. When workers want to study, the administration helps them.

Conversely, the government has a well-defined strategy for handling and debating the choice. When it comes to making decisions, management lets staff members help. Between the superior and the subordinates, there is mutual trust and cooperation. The management welcomes

comments and points of view from the staff. When making and carrying out decisions, management acts in unison.

That is was also found that the extent of job satisfaction in the Saudi Telecom Company in terms of job satisfaction was high, with the arithmetic mean (3.94) and a standard deviation (0.65), because workers at the Saudi Telecom Company enjoy what they do, believe their jobs provide a social wage that is satisfactory, and believe that their employment advances their professional goals. Because the organization offers opportunities for skill development and has transparent administrative procedures, they feel independent while performing and hope to stay for a long time. Because of the company's conducive and healthy work environment, employees are receiving good administrative services from the business.

The researcher subjected the hypotheses that state: “There is a statistically significant correlation and influence at the level of significance (0.05) between administrative leadership and job satisfaction in the Saudi Telecom Company and to simple linear regression analysis, that shown in table (2).

Table 2: Results of simple linear regression analysis of the role of administrative leadership in job satisfaction

administrative leadership	Value β	Value Beta	Value t	level of significance P-value	The result
job satisfaction	1.874	0.621	6.668	.000	There is a role.
R				0.621a	
value R ²				0.385	
value F				56.422	
P-value				.000b	

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (spss)

It is clear from the table that the value of the correlation coefficient R is (.621), which indicates that there is also a moderate direct correlation. The value of the coefficient of determination R² is equal to (.385). That explains (38%) of the role of administrative leadership in job satisfaction. The remaining percentage is explained by other variables, as can be seen from the table that the calculated F-value is equal to (56.422). At the same time, the P-value is equal to (.000). This value is statistically significant and is less than (0.05). That means that the regression is significant, meaning there is an effect from the independent variable on the dependent variable. Thus, a statistically significant role was found at the level of statistical significance (0.05) for administrative leadership in job satisfaction.

The results of this study were similar to the study of Saad Alessa (2021), which proved the existence of a positive role. The leadership strives to increase the level of employee satisfaction and thus create a suitable working atmosphere (Vinh et al., 2023; Mirdad, 2018). Laws and rules, or the organizational method, are the guidelines that guide the performance of leadership (Nabella et al., 2022). It is typified by the administrative body delivering commands to people without offering a reaction when they are carried out. Embracing it, taking part in its execution, and assessing the outcomes that follow (Williams & Wade-Golden, 2023).

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to identify the impact and role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction for employees in the Saudi Telecom Company. The descriptive analytical approach was used, where data and information were collected, and the questionnaire was used as a tool for collecting data and analyzing it using the (SPSS) system to answer the study's questions and hypotheses. Taking a simple random sample from the research population, who are employees of the Saudi Telecom Company, the questionnaire was distributed electronically to the company's employees, and the number of those who responded to the questionnaire was a sample of (92) male and female employees, through an electronic form via the website (Google Drive), and then sending the electronic link to the targeted sample via mobile phone applications, email, and some social networking sites. The results were shown. The results of the study showed that the role of administrative leadership in achieving job satisfaction was high. The results of the study also showed that there is a strong connection between the dimensions of administrative leadership and achieving job satisfaction.

Study contribution

This study aids in the adoption of contemporary management practices and ideas, enabling businesses to stay up to date with technological advancements, enhance employee happiness, and ultimately attain performance and excellence. Additionally, it helps to diversify training programs linked to improving employee performance and conduct specialized courses to sharpen the abilities of corporate authorities. Because it is crucial to attaining high-performance levels for the business, it is also focused on obtaining job satisfaction for workers. It facilitates the leader's involvement in collaborative decision-making with his subordinates. Creating a system of incentives and rewards that takes into account the performance and behaviour of the workforce.

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